

ACRIDINE DERIVATIVES AS ANTIMALARIALS.

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Since the observation of Mauss and Mietzsch (*Klin-Woch.*, 1933, 12, 1276) that the dihydrochloride of 2-chloro-5 (*ω*-diethylaminoisoamyl)-amino-7-methoxyacridine, better known as 'Atebrin,' has a powerful action on all asexual forms of the malarial parasites, a good deal of attention (*cf.* Magidson and Grigorovski, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 396, 537) has been given to the syntheses of various other acridine derivatives of the above type, having particularly a dialkylaminoalkylamino side-chain in position 5. In view of the fact that reduction generally diminishes the toxicity of a compound and that the Bz-tetrahydrohydrocinchonine (I) has the same influence on the fever as the cinchonine itself (*cf.* Braunn and Lenke, *Annalen*, 1930, 478, 176), a study on the physiological activity of a hydrated acridine derivative of the above type was considered to be of special interest. As very little is known about the chemistry of hydrated acridines, a method was found out for their synthesis and several compounds of the above type have been prepared.

It was shown by Sen and Basu (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 435) that ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate when treated with an aromatic amine at the room temperature afforded an anil (II), which may be readily converted into a tetrahydroacridone (III). This reaction has been utilised for the syntheses of various 1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-chloroacridine derivatives of the type (IV, R=Cl). When these chloro compounds are treated with phenol they easily afford the phenoxy derivatives (IV, R=OPh) from which several 5-dialkylaminoacridines [IV, R=NH(CH₂)_nN⁺Et₂] have been obtained. It has also been noted that the aminoacridine [IV, R=NH(CH₂)_nN⁺Et₂] might be more conveniently obtained from 5-chloroacridine itself. In fact, this process has been usually followed in the course of this investigation. The aminoacridines are almost colourless and readily form

stable dihydrochlorides which are highly soluble in water and extremely bitter in taste.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1:2:3:4-Tetrahydro-5-chloroacridine (IV, R=Cl).—Equimolecular quantities of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate and aniline were mixed and kept in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride for 8-10 days. The mixture was then heated at 250-260° for about 2 hours, and the residual mass on cooling was washed with ether and collected. It was 1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridone (III), m. p. 358-60° (*cf.* Sen and Basu, *loc. cit.*). To a mixture of Bz-tetrahydroacridone (4 g.) and finely powdered phosphorus pentachloride (5 g.), a few c.c. of phosphorus oxychloride was added just in sufficient quantity to make a thin paste and the whole was slowly heated to 120-130° and this temperature was maintained for about 2 hours when most of the phosphorus oxychloride distilled over. The contents in the flask solidified. It was well cooled and decomposed with ice, filtered and the filtrate made alkaline with ammonia. The precipitate was filtered off, washed and crystallised from petroleum ether, m. p. 68-69°. (Found: Cl, 16.63. Calc. for C₁₃H₁₂NCl: Cl, 16.32 per cent). This compound has been described by Perkin and Sedgwick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2446) to melt at 226°; and by Braun and others (*Ber.*, 1931, 64, 227) to melt at 68°.

1:2:3:4-Tetrahydro-5-phenoxyacridine (IV, R=OPh).—To a hot solution of phenol (3 g.) in caustic potash (0.3 g.) 1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-chloroacridine (0.5 g.) was added slowly and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 140° for about 2 hours. The hot melt was poured into about 50 c.c. of 10% caustic soda solution and kept overnight. The supernatant liquid was decanted off and the residual mass was triturated with 5% caustic soda solution, filtered and washed free from alkali. The crude phenoxy compound separated from petroleum ether in microscopic needles, m. p. 102°. It was converted to its hydrochloride by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas into its ethereal solution and crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether (1:1), m. p. 223-25°. (Found: Cl, 11.53. C₁₃H₁₇ON, HCl requires Cl, 11.40 per cent).

1 : 2 : 3 : 4- *Tetrahydro-5* (δ -*diethylaminobutyl*)*aminoacridine*.—The above tetrahydrochloroacridine (0.6 g.) was heated in a sealed tube with 0.8 g. of diethylaminobutylamine and a little copper powder at 150-160° for several hours. The mass was treated with water and the supernatant layer was decanted off. It was thus repeatedly washed with water in order to remove the unreacted amine. The residual semi-solid mass was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution was filtered and treated with dilute acetic acid. The acetic acid solution was made alkaline with ammonia in the cold when the base separated as a semi-solid mass which was again washed several times with water. It was once more extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate and treated with dry hydrochloric acid gas. The dihydrochloride thus obtained being extremely hygroscopic could not be isolated. Its aqueous solution was accordingly treated with a solution of sodium salt of methylenedioxy-naphthoic acid in the cold when a salt of the aminoacridine with methylenedioxy-naphthoic acid was isolated in a crystalline form. It was collected and thoroughly washed. It is tasteless and insoluble in water, m. p. 216-20°. (Found: N, 5.56. $C_{21}H_{31}N_3$, $C_{23}H_{16}O_8$ requires N, 5.88 per cent).

7-*Methoxy-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydroacridone*.—A mixture of ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (17 g.) and *p*-anisidine (12.3 g.) was left overnight. There was much turbidity owing to the separation of water from the reaction mixture and it was left in vacuum over fused calcium chloride for 10 days, when a clear dark solution was obtained. It was then heated in an oil-bath at 260-270° for about 4 hours when the contents of the flask solidified. On cooling the solid product was treated with ether and was filtered, yield 18 g. The compound crystallised from alcohol in prismatic needles, m. p. 295°. It is soluble in dilute mineral acids. (Found: N, 6.29. $C_{14}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 6.10 per cent).

7-*Methoxy-5-chloro-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydroacridine* was prepared from the above acridone (4 g.) and finely powdered phosphorus pentachloride (5 g.) as in the case of (IV, R=Cl). It separated in pale yellow prismatic needles from dilute alcohol, m. p. 122°. (Found: Cl, 15.01. $C_{14}H_{14}ONCl$ requires Cl, 14.34 per cent).

7-*Methoxy-5-phenoxy-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydroacridine*.—The chloroacridine (2 g.) was heated with phenol (8 g.) at 140-150° for about 3 hours. The reaction mixture was then poured into a *N*-NaOH solution when the phenoxy derivative separated as an oil. It was left overnight when it solidified. The supernatant liquid was decanted off and it was triturated

with caustic soda solution, filtered and washed free from alkali. It crystallises from petroleum ether in long prismatic needles, m.p. 120°. (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{20}H_{19}O_2N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent). It is a crystalline solid and readily dissolves in dilute acids. On passing dry hydrogen chloride to its ethereal solution the hydrochloride was easily obtained, which melted to a green liquid at 220° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 10.13. $C_{20}H_{19}O_2N$, HCl requires Cl, 10.4 per cent).

It forms a picrate, m.p. 190-192°. When treated with δ -diethylamino-butylamine in a sealed tube at 150-160° it affords the 5-aminoacridine derivative which is also easily obtained by the method described below.

Dihydrochloride of 7-Methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-(δ -diethylaminobutyl)-aminoacridine.—7-Methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-chloroacridine (0.6 g.) was heated with δ -diethylaminobutylamine (0.8 g.) and a little copper powder at 160° for several hours. The mixture was treated as in the previous case. The ethereal solution finally obtained was dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate and treated with dry hydrogen chloride. The crude dihydrochloride was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and dry ether and the product was rapidly dried in a vacuum desiccator, m.p. 193-94°. (Found: Cl, 16.31. $C_{22}H_{33}ON_3$, 2HCl requires Cl, 16.59 per cent).

Dihydrochloride of 7-Methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-(γ -diethylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine.—The chloro compound (0.6 g.) was heated with γ -diethylaminopropylamine (0.8 g.) in a sealed tube at about 160° with a little copper powder. After the usual treatment of the reaction mixture the dihydrochloride was isolated and crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether and rapidly dried, m.p. 228-29°. [Found: Cl, 16.3. $C_{21}H_{31}ON_3$, 2HCl, H_2O requires Cl, 16.44 per cent. Found (in sample dried at 105-110°): N, 10.24; Cl, 17.02. $C_{21}H_{31}ON_3$, 2HCl requires N, 10.15; Cl, 17.15 per cent].

7-Methoxy-2-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroacridone.—Molecular proportions of ethyl 5-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate and *p*-anisidine were mixed together and left over as usual. On heating the reaction mixture at 250-260°, the contents of the flask set to a crystalline solid which was collected, washed with ether and finally crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 335°. (Found: N, 5.89. $C_{15}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 5.76 per cent).

7-Methoxy-2-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-chloroacridine.—The acridone derivative was heated with a mixture of phosphorus penta- and oxychloride at 120-30° as in the formation of the previous chloroacridine. The solid residue on treatment with ice and ammonia afforded a yellow

substance which on crystallisation from methyl alcohol separated in slender needles, m.p. 90° . (Found : Cl, 13.70. $C_{13}H_{10}ONCl$ requires Cl, 13.58 per cent).

7-Methoxy-2-methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydro-5-phenoxyacridine, was prepared by heating the chloroacridine (2 g.) with phenol (8 g.) as in the previous case. It crystallised from petroleum ether in long prismatic needles, m.p. 103° . (Found : N, 4.56. $C_{21}H_{21}O_2N$ requires N, 4.38 per cent).

Dihydrochloride of 7-Methoxy-2-methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydro-5-(δ -diethylaminobutyl)-aminoacridine.—The chloroacridine (0.7 g.) was heated with δ -diethylaminobutylamine (0.8 g.) in a sealed tube with a trace of copper powder at 160° as usual. The dihydrochloride was isolated in the usual manner and crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether and dried in vacuum, m.p. 203.4° . The substance was dried at 110° and analysed. (Found : N, 9.08. $C_{23}H_{35}ON_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 9.5 per cent).

Dihydrochloride of 7-Methoxy-2-methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydro-5-(γ -diethylaminopropyl)-aminoacridine.—The chloroacridine (0.8 g.) was heated with diethylaminopropylamine (0.8 g.) at 150 – 160° in a sealed tube with a little copper powder. After usual treatment the dihydrochloride was isolated and crystallised, m.p. 242 – 43° . [Found : Cl, 15.80. $C_{22}H_{33}ON_2 \cdot 2HCl \cdot H_2O$ requires Cl, 15.92 per cent. Found (in a sample dried at 110°) : N, 9.86; Cl, 16.51. $C_{22}H_{33}ON_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires N, 9.81; Cl, 16.59 per cent.]

Ethyl 2-(4'-chloroanilido)-4-methyl- Δ^1 -cyclohexene-1-carboxylate.

The carboxylate derivative of *m*-methylcyclohexanone was mixed with a molecular proportion of *p*-chloroaniline and kept in a desiccator in *vacuo*. Gradually crystals began to separate. These were collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine prismatic needles, m.p. 90° . (Found : N, 4.90. $C_{16}H_{20}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.77 per cent).

7-Chloro-2-methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydroacridone.—The above anilido compound was heated in an oil-bath at 270° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour when the contents in

the flask solidified to a crystalline mass. This was cooled, washed with alcohol and crystallised from boiling glacial acetic acid. It is sparingly soluble in the common organic solvents and melts with decomposition at 375° in a sealed capillary. (Found : N, 5.38. $C_{14}H_{14}ONCl$ requires N, 5.65 per cent).

5 : 7-Dichloro-2-methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydroacridine.—The acridone derivative was made into a paste with phosphorus penta- and oxychloride and heated as usual. The reacted mass was further treated with hydrochloric acid and the whole was filtered. The filtrate was cooled and neutralised with ammonia. A semi-solid mass was isolated which was left over in a refrigerator. Next day the solid found was collected and crystallised from methyl alcohol (charcoal), m.p. 89° . (Found: Cl, 26.44. $C_{14}H_{13}NCl_2$ requires Cl, 26.69 per cent).

7-Chloro-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydroacridone.—This acridone derivative was obtained in the usual way from the reaction mixture obtained by mixing ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate and *p*-chloroanil (1 : 1) at the room temperature and keeping the mixture over fused calcium chloride in *vacuo* for about a fortnight. The substance was difficultly soluble in alcohol. It crystallised from a large volume of the same solvent in silky needles, m.p. 380° * (Found : Cl, 15.22. $C_{13}H_{12}ONCl$ requires Cl, 15.20 per cent).

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* This compound has been synthesised in another way and found to melt at 365° by Prof. Dr. O. J. Magidson of Scientific (Chemical-Pharmaceutical) Research Institute, Moscow, U. S. S. R. (*private communication*).